

Miniaturized Antenna for Biomedical Implantable Devices

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Abstract— This work proposes the design of an antenna for energy reception or wireless communication in biomedical implant applications. Aiming at the application of miniaturization techniques to reduce the total size of the antenna. The proposed antenna is of the patch type with rectangular shape, designed to operate on the frequency of 2.4 GHz. In the initial design of the antenna, theoretical concepts were used to calculate its dimensions, and then the use of HFSS (High-frequency Structure Simulator) simulation software was used for analysis of S parameters such as gain and reflection coefficient of the antenna, and optimizations of the techniques employed. As results it was analyzed that the positioning of antenna components, such as the feed are essential to reduce return losses, and the addition and positioning of short circuit slots in patch pin can lead to a decrease in the frequency of resonance. However, more simulations and applications of other techniques such as opening slots the patch plane are still needed to provide the desired resonance frequency of 2.4 GHz, decreased return loss, and increased operating bandwidth.

Keywords — Implantable antenna, miniaturization, power reception, wireless communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

For wireless power of the deployed sensors, some power and antenna challenges must be considered. Among these, the significant attenuation of the signal is highlighted, caused by the body tissues that hinder the propagation of this signal through the human body to the sensors [1] and, consequently, limits the amount of energy to be delivered to the sensor in vivo. Another challenge is related to the reduced size of elements such as antennas, which impact on a low energy absorption efficiency [2],[3]. The next few paragraphs will be more detailed about these challenges.

Currently, there has been an increased need for the use of implantable biomedical devices for applications such as diagnostics, monitoring and medical intervention [4]. But it is a great challenge to have a device with reduced size, biocompatible and operated by battery for long life. In addition, with the use of battery, there is a need for recharging, and it is necessary that a surgery be done to remove the battery to recharge it. However, this procedure can cause additional trauma and risk of infections to the patient. This makes it more promising to replace battery use with a wireless power transfer

source to provide power for implantable biomedical devices [4].

The use of implantable biomedical devices has several applications [5],[6], such as glucose monitoring [7], cardiac pacemakers [8] and neural registration [9]. It is evident that it is indispensable to use these devices for the monitoring of patients in these various applications. Therefore, remote monitoring consists of collecting physiological information from inside the human body, and transmitting it outwards to a receiver [10]. For the transmission of this information an antenna is necessary for this to be accomplished since this is the fundamental part for the information to be transmitted out of the human body [11].

In implantable biomedical devices should be considered the reduced size of the antenna. For this, some miniaturization techniques are used, such as opening slots in the radiation patch, and adding short circuit pins [12][13]. According to the addition and position of the short circuit pin in the antenna, the resonant length is halved if it is positioned in the center of the fundamental mode, where the value of the electric field is zero [14]. The miniaturization technique that uses the opening of slots in the radiant patch causes the current to extend in the patch, in relation to the return of the current to the short circuit pin, causing it to reduce the frequency of resonance [15].

In the design of a bioimplantable antenna, in addition to miniaturization, the dielectric incompatibility in relation to the media presented by the antennas must also be considered [16]. For in a system of energy transfer or communication with bio implantable devices, it presents two antennas, which is the wireless energy transmitter, or signal receiver (positioned outside the human body) and the implantable antenna (positioned inside the human body). So, this incompatibility occurs because then and different means. To reduce these incompatibilities, the use of substrate with high permittiveness and metamaterials is employed. To reduce this incompatibility, a high dielectric constant substrate is required [17].

Thus, the present work will seek the understanding and development of a miniaturized implantable antenna that has an operating frequency of 2.4 GHz, which can be used both for use in the reception of wireless energy, as for wireless communication. For its design will be employed several miniaturization techniques. That as they are employed,

simulations will be made in a full-wave electromagnetic simulation (HFSS) software, to analyze the effects of these techniques regarding the resonance frequency initially projected of 5 GHz. And a parametric study will also be made in relation to the components that influence the resonance frequency and performance of the antenna as the dimensions of the patch and the ground plane, and the positioning of the feed, short circuit pins and slots in patch plane, for optimization of these dimensions and positions, to obtain the best performance results of the antenna.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN AND PARAMETRIC STUDIES

An implantable antenna developed for applications such as electrostimulation and wireless electroencephalography, with an operating frequency of 2.45 GHz. This study aims to apply miniaturization techniques to decrease the total volume of the antenna, increase the gain and frequency bandwidth in three different materials: vacuum, skin, and muscle. Several miniaturization techniques were used in the antenna design to reduce the dimensions of the implantable antenna, such as the use of short circuit pins and slots in the patch. In the following sections it will be better detailed about the use of these techniques and the results obtained.

A. Proposed antenna design process

At first, a coaxial feed was made to a rectangular microstrip antenna coaxial feed, calculating the dimensional parameters, as shown in Fig. 1. In its design was considered variables regarding the material of the substrate, such as the dielectric constant and thickness of the material. The material used was the laminate Rogers RO3010 ($\epsilon_r = 10.2$, $\tan \delta = 0.0035$) with a thickness of 0.64mm. This antenna was initially designed to have a resonant frequency of 5 GHz, being adopted a frequency of almost twice, the desired final operating frequency of 2.45 GHz. This was due to allowing the dimensions of the antenna to be reduced in this initial design. To then be applied miniaturization techniques (short circuit pins, slots), to obtain the desired operating frequency. The dimensional parameters of the antenna design were calculated using the following equations [18], and the results obtained are represented in Table I:

Fig. 1. Dimensional parameters of coaxial feed microstrip antenna.

Dimensions of coaxial feed microstrip rectangular antenna:

The width (W) of the rectangular Patch Antenna can be obtained in this way:

$$W = \frac{c}{2fr\sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r+1}{2}}} \quad (1)$$

Where ' f_r ' corresponds to the resonance frequency, ' c ' is the speed of light in a vacuum ($=3 \times 10^8$ m/sec) and ' ϵ_r ' is the dielectric constant of the dielectric material. The effective dielectric constant ' ϵ_{reff} ' is calculated by Equation (2).

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{\epsilon_r+1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r-1}{2} \left[1 + 12 \frac{h}{W} \right]^{-0.5} \quad (2)$$

Where the ' h ' corresponds to the thickness of the substrate used, which is 0.635 mm.

The length ' L ' of the rectangular Patch Antenna can be obtained by Equation (3):

$$L = L\epsilon_{reff} - 2\Delta L \quad (3)$$

Where ' L_{reff} ' is the effective length of the rectangular patch antenna, where it is calculated through the Equation (4).

$$L\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{c}{2fr\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} \quad (4)$$

The variation length ' ΔL ' is calculated by Equation (5).

$$\Delta L = 0.412h \frac{\left[(\epsilon_{reff}+0.3) \left(\left(\frac{W}{h} \right) + 0.264 \right) \right]}{\left[(\epsilon_{reff}-0.258) \left(\left(\frac{W}{h} \right) + 0.8 \right) \right]} \quad (5)$$

The dimensions of the ground plane are obtained by the following equations. The Equation (6) is used to calculate the length ' L_g ' of the ground plane.

$$L_g = 6h + L \quad (6)$$

To calculate the width of the ground plane ' W_g ' is calculated by the equation (7).

$$W_g = 6h + W \quad (7)$$

To calculate the position of the feed point along the axes X (x_p) and Y (y_p), the Equations 8 and 9 are used.

$$x_p = \frac{L}{2\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} \quad (8)$$

$$y_p = \frac{W}{2} \quad (9)$$

TABLE I. ANTENNA DESIGN PARAMETERS AND VALUES

Parameters	Value
Resonance frequency	5 GHz
Substrate dielectric constant ϵ_r	10.2
Thickness h of the dielectric	0.64 mm
ϵ_{reff}	9.23 mm
Width (W) of the patch antenna	12.68 mm
Length (L) of patch antenna	9.33 mm
Width (W_g) of ground plane	16.52 mm
Length (L_g) of ground plane	13.17 mm

Identifying the Feed Point location:

The correct position of the feed on the antenna provides better performance, this is due to an impedance match equal to 50Ω . To obtain this position, the full-wave electromagnetic simulation (HFSS) was used for a parametric position analysis.

In this analysis, a position range was defined along the X and Y axes for optimization of feed point, varying ' x_p ' from 0 mm to 5.84 mm with a step of 0.4 mm, and ' y_p ' from 0 mm to 4.36 mm with a step of 0.4 mm. After the simulation of these points, the values obtained of impedance and loss of return were compared to choose the point with the best performance.

B. Parametric study of antenna dimension

After obtaining the initial parameters of the patch antenna dimensions and the ideal feeding position, it is essential to make a parametric study to optimize these obtained parameters. In this study four parameters were considered, which are the 'W', the 'L' related to the patch dimension and the ' W_g, L_g ' related to the ground plane. Thus, in the simulation software, a percentage variable was used to the analysis parameters, allowing an optimization of the dimensions of the antenna components. With this, it is intended to observe with the results obtained, what is the relationship of the dimensions with the range of resonance frequency and the loss of return. Considering in the optimization values of smaller dimensions in relation to those calculated in the theory, this will allow the decrease of the final size of the antenna.

C. Application of miniaturization techniques

The decrease in the total volume of an antenna is possible from the use of miniaturization techniques such as the addition of short circuit pins and slots in the patch plane.

Short circuit pin addition:

Based on the studies [14], the addition of a short circuit pin in the correct position, allows to reduce the resonant length by half in vacuum. So based on that, a short pin was initially added to the antenna, with symmetry with respect to the optimized position of the feed point. The frequency range was then analyzed according to the position variation along the X-axis. It is observed that the closer you get to the operating frequency of 2.45 GHz the better.

Adding slots to patch:

To achieve better performance and size reduction in the antenna, rectangular slots are created in the radiant patch. The slot will be added to the patch plane. Width and Length values

that are smaller than the total patch area will be pre-established. After that, a parametric study will be done to optimize the parameters of width and length of the slot. With this study, the effects on the change of these dimensions in relation to the frequency of resonance will be observed. To find the parameters that provide gain in the antenna, in addition to the reduction of return losses, and especially in reaching the desired resonance frequency of 2.45 GHz.

III. SETTING UP THE SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

The configuration of the sandbox is represented by Fig. 2. In which the antenna was positioned at the origin ($x = 0, y = 0, z = 0$) and placed inside a radiation box with dimensions of 300 mm x 300 mm x 150 mm, which simulates the radiation of the antenna in vacuum.

In this first moment for the purpose of learning and familiarization of the HFSS software, the simulation was done only in a vacuum, because the theoretical calculations of the antenna were considered only the speed of propagation of light in a vacuum. After this, was simulated the properties of the tissues of the human body, considering the same dimensions of the radiation box in Figure 2, but taking into account the antenna positioned within the tissues (skin and muscle) with the dimensions and dielectric properties at the operating frequency of 2.45 GHz [13], as represented in Figure 3 and Table II.

Fig. 2. Simulation environment, considering only the radiation box being the vacuum.

Fig. 3. Dimensions of the tissues used for antenna simulation. A, Simulation in skin. B, Simulation in skin + muscle.

TABLE II. DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF DIFFERENT TISSUES AT 2.45 GHz

Tissues	Thickness (mm)	ϵ_r	σ (S/m)	Density (kg/m ³)
Skin	4	38.0	1.44	1100
Muscle	15	52.7	1.74	1041

IV. SIMULETED RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

With the initial design of the antenna based on theoretical calculations and using the HFSS software for the electromagnetic simulations, the techniques described in

Section II were applied to three types of materials: vacuum, skin and muscle. In each simulation step, the optimization tool was used to capture the best results.

The Feed Point location:

A. Vacuum

At first, the dimensional parameters of the antenna were maintained, as reported in Table I. Next, a parametric analysis of the position of the feeding point was performed. As shown in Fig. 4, we can analyze that in the position ($x_f = 0.0\text{mm}$, $y_f = 1.2\text{mm}$), it obtained the best performance, having the lowest return loss, and presenting a resonance frequency at 5 GHz.

Fig. 4. Effects of the change in feed placement on the reflection coefficient.

B. Skin

Now, repeating the process of optimizing the feeding point, but adding a 4.00 mm layer of skin over the antenna. It was expected that because of the dielectric properties and density of the material, there would be an attenuation of electromagnetic radiation, decreasing the frequency of resonance. Thus, observing the results obtained, it was noticed that the greater the displacement of the feed in the X and Y axes, the lower the resonance frequency and the loss of return. As shown in Fig. 5, at the first point ($x_f = 0.0\text{mm}$, $y_f = 0.0\text{mm}$) the antenna resonated at 3.38 GHz and had a return loss of -17.34 dB. The last point of analysis ($x_f = 6.0\text{mm}$, $y_f = 4.0\text{mm}$), resonated at 2.25 GHz and had a return loss of -12.21 dB.

Fig. 5. Effects of the change in feed placement on the reflection coefficient when add a layer of human skin.

C. Muscle and Skin

Adding a 15.0 mm layer of muscle over the antenna and a 4.0 mm layer of skin over the muscle, the feed position optimization process was carried out again. Thus, observing

the results, again the resonance frequency and the return loss decreased, as the feeding point moved away from the origin of the X and Y axes.

Representing the main results in Fig. 6, the first point analyzed ($x_f = 3.0\text{mm}$, $y_f = 0.0\text{mm}$) the antenna resonated at 3.22 GHz and had a return loss of -10.65 dB. At the last point of the analysis range ($x_f = 6.0\text{mm}$, $y_f = 4.0\text{mm}$) the antenna resonated at 2.36 GHz and had a return loss of -10.16 dB. Despite having a thicker layer of human tissue than the previous step, the resonance frequency at the point ($x_f = 6.0\text{mm}$, $y_f = 4.0\text{mm}$) was slightly higher and had a lower return loss, when compared with the simulation only with the skin layer.

Fig. 6. Effects of the change in feed placement on the reflection coefficient when add a layer of human skin and muscle.

Parametric study of antenna dimension (Vacuum):

After performing the optimization of the feed point, a study of the parametric of the variables that determine the dimensions of the antenna was made, namely: 'W', 'L', 'W_g', 'L_g'. This optimization was performed without the presence of human tissue, to know what the interference of these parameters in the operation of the antenna, allowing a minaturization of the device and fine adjustment of the resonance frequency and loss of return.

With the results obtained in Fig. 7 and considering as 100% the original size of the antenna, as described in Table I. It is evident that the alteration of the dimensional parameters of the antenna, changes the resonance frequency. Thus, by diminishing the antenna, the frequency increases, and by increasing the dimensions the frequency decreases.

Fig. 7. Effects of changing antenna dimensions on the reflection coefficient.

Short circuit pin addition:

A. Vacuum

Now, another antenna miniaturization technique has been used, inserting a short-circuit pin between the patch and the ground plane. Thus, the optimization of the short pin was performed by varying the position only along the X axis. The resonant frequency can be halved by placing a short pin, so that the electric field is null [14].

As evidenced by Fig. 8, we had that the best result after the simulation is the position of the short pin in ($x_f = 0.8\text{mm}$, $y_f = 1.2\text{mm}$). Where the return loss was less than -17dB and the resonance frequency at 3.75GHz .

Fig. 8. Effects of use of shorting pins on the reflection coefficient.

B. Skin

Choosing the point with the lowest resonance frequency after simulating the feed with the skin, an optimization of the short-circuit pin was performed. Thus, the results obtained showed that the resonance frequency increased subtly, but the return loss decreases considerably, by about -8dB .

Fig. 9. Effects of use of shorting pins on the reflection coefficient when add a layer of human skin.

C. Skin and Muscle

Repeating the procedure performed in the previous item, the frequency with the lowest resonance was chosen for the optimization of the short pin. Thus, a return loss of -35dB was obtained as the maximum range, as shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Effects of use of shorting pins on the reflection coefficient when add a layer of human skin and muscle.

Adding slots to patch plane:

In this last miniaturization technique, slots were added in the patch plane. Thus, for the simulations that the parametric study using human tissue, perpendicular grooves were created with symmetrical distances between the feeding point and the short-circuit pin.

A. Skin

As a result of the addition of slots in the patch plane, we had a gradual decrease in the resonance frequency, conversely, the return loss increased, as represented in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Effects of using slots in patch plane on the reflection coefficient when add a layer of human skin.

B. Skin and Muscle

The presence of muscle and skin, when performed the optimization of the slot in the patch plane, did not have much effect in this case. Increasing the return loss by more than 20dB and shifting the operating frequency to 2.48GHz , as depicted in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Effects of using slots in patch plane on the reflection coefficient when add a layer of human skin and muscle.

Parametric study of antenna dimension (Skin and Muscle):

With the application of miniaturization methods and obtaining satisfactory results, with frequencies close to 2.45GHz and return loss less than -10dB. The same procedure of parametric study of the dimensions of the antenna was repeated, but now for the simulations involving the human tissue (skin). Thus, allowing the decrease of the final design of the antenna.

A. Skin

With the results obtained by the parametric study of the dimensions of the antenna, it was observed that using the previous miniaturization techniques it was possible to reduce by 30% the original size of the antenna. Operating at a frequency of 2.4 GHz and a return loss of -16. dB, as shown in Fig.13.

Fig. 13. Effects of changing antenna dimensions on the reflection coefficient.

V. CONCLUSION

The design of the proposed antenna was taken into account several steps, starting with the initial design in which the choice of antenna type, thickness and dielectric material used in the substrate, and resonance frequency is made. From this it is possible to apply miniaturization techniques to reduce the size of the antenna, causing the resonance frequency initially projected of 5 GHz, to resonate at a frequency of 2.4 GHz of desired operation.

In the simulation environment, the studies performed in the vacuum were used for validations of theoretical foundations, having dielectric properties that did not interfere in the operation of the antenna. The insertion of human tissue boxes, on the other hand, had properties similar to true human tissue, serving as an attenuating layer of electromagnetic waves. Thus, in general, the insertion of layers of human tissue decreased the frequency of resonance of the antenna, but its expressura did not show a relevant change in the results.

With the application of theoretical foundations and the optimized positioning of the feed pin in vacuum, it was possible to elaborate an initial model of antenna that operated at 5 GHz. From this, inserting short-circuit pins, changes in the dimensions of the antenna and addition of slots in the patch plane, it was possible to decrease the resonance frequency and the return loss. By applying a layer of tissue with dielectric properties over the antenna, this signal was attenuated, and with some manipulations it was possible to reach the expected

result. In general, it is concluded that with the application of the three miniaturization techniques highlighted in the previous sections, they contributed to the development of an antenna that operates at 2.4 GHz and a return loss of less than -10dB, as proposed as the objective of this work.

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